

Studies on β -lactams : Synthesis of N-substituted di and tri-chloroacetamides and their cyclisation to β -lactams

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A number of N-substituted di and tri-haloacetamides structurally similar to the well tolerated antiamebic agent Mantomide have been synthesised and subsequently cyclised to the corresponding β -lactams. It has been found that the ease of cyclisation of the haloamides with different bases varies with the substituent on (i) the N-phenyl ring and (ii) on the methine carbon atom respectively.

A number of physiologically active compounds like penicillin, cephalosporin-c¹ and the major steroidal alkaloid of pachysandra Terminalis² are known to contain a β -lactam ring I as the reactive moiety. These lactams can be visualized as a ring analog of the exceptionally well tolerated antiamebic agent Mantomide II. We were therefore interested to prepare and study the physiological properties of various haloamides of the type III and the corresponding β -lactams IV. We primarily synthesised

The various aminomalononic esters V and aminophenyl acetic esters VI were synthesised by the technique developed by Chatterjee and co-workers^{5,6}. These amino esters were characterised by comparison with authentic samples. Bose's⁷ method of N-acylation under non-basic conditions, could not be carried out successfully with di- and trichloroacetic acid. Bosshard's⁸ method of conversion of strong acids to acylhalides was applied by us and we were successful in obtaining pure di- and tri-chloroacetyl

$R' = H \text{ or } Cl.$

(III)

(IV)

haloamides from substituted aminomalononic esters V and substituted aminophenylacetic esters VI by the general method of Sheehan and Bose^{3,4}.

chloride which could be easily refluxed with equivalent quantities of amino esters to give excellent yields of the amido esters. The following dihalo and trihalo amides were prepared by us (Table 1).

These amides in general have been characterised by elemental analysis, infra red spectra and in some

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cases by n.m.r. spectra. The esters V and VI show a peak at 3μ (-NH-) in the I.R. Spectra and a

broad or narrow peak at 5.75μ depending on the number of ester carbonyls present in the ester.

TABLE I

Compound No.	III $\xrightarrow{\hspace{2cm}}$ IV			R'
	R	a	b	
1.	C ₆ H ₅	-COOC ₂ H ₅	COOC ₂ H ₅	H†
2.	<i>p</i> CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	-COOC ₂ H ₅	COOC ₂ H ₅	H†
3.	<i>p</i> Cl-C ₆ H ₄	-COOC ₂ H ₅	COOC ₂ H ₅	H
4.	<i>p</i> Br-C ₆ H ₄	-COOC ₂ H ₅	COOC ₂ H ₅	H
5.	C ₆ H ₅	-COOC ₂ H ₅	COOC ₂ H ₅	Cl
6.	<i>p</i> Me-C ₆ H ₄	-COOC ₂ H ₅	COOC ₂ H ₅	Cl
7.	<i>p</i> Cl-C ₆ H ₄	-COOC ₂ H ₅	COOC ₂ H ₅	Cl
8.	<i>p</i> Br-C ₆ H ₄	-COOC ₂ H ₅	COOC ₂ H ₅	Cl
9.	C ₆ H ₅	-COOC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	H
10.	<i>p</i> CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	-COOC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	H
11.	<i>p</i> Cl-C ₆ H ₄	-COOC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	H
12.	<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄	-COOC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	H
13.	C ₆ H ₅	-COOC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	Cl
14.	<i>p</i> CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	-COOC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	Cl
15.	<i>p</i> Cl-C ₆ H ₄	-COOC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	Cl
16.	<i>p</i> Br-C ₆ H ₄	-COOC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	Cl

† III : Reported earlier (Ref. 9).

‡ IV : Reported earlier B. N. Ghosh Majumdar. Ph.D. I.I.T. Kharagpur 1957.

On amidification of these esters the -NH- peak at 3μ is lost and a new peak appears at $5.9-6.0\mu$ due to the open chain disubstituted amide carbonyl. Cyclisation of the amides, results in the shifting of the amide carbonyl peak at $5.9-6.0$ to 5.65μ due to formation of the lactam. I.R. Spectra of the hitherto unreported amides of table I are in accord with the above observations.

The n m r. spectrum is important especially in cyclization of the amides. The loss of the methine proton (singlet, 4.15 T) in the amides III before cyclisation is clearly indicated in the n.m.r. spectrum of the lactams IV.

Cyclisation of the dihaloacetamides of the malonic ester system was carried out with triethyl amine. We found that III-1+2 were readily cyclised (30 min) whereas III-3 and 4 having electron withdrawing groups on the N-phenyl ring required prolonged treatment (30 days). Incidentally compound III-1, has been reported earlier as a solid.⁹ In spite of our best efforts we could not solidify

the viscous amide. From the behaviour of the amides towards cyclisation it seems that though an electron withdrawing atom in the phenyl ring activities the methine hydrogen as well as the carbonyl of the amide function, by increased delocalization of the non-bonded electrons of nitrogen into the phenyl ring, it retards, an SN₂ type of displacement of the halogen atom.

Cyclisation of the dichloroacetamido phenyl acetates (Table I; III-9, 10, 11, 12) where the methine hydrogen is activated by only one ester group was carried out with equivalent quantities of alcoholic potassium hydroxide.¹⁰

The reaction was complete in about 30 min. The extent of the reaction was measured on the basis of eliminated potassium chloride weighed as silver chloride. The lactam IV; 9 and 10 were isolated as deep red transparent liquids but could not be purified to the analytical standards either by molecular distillation or by column chromatography and were therefore characterised by I.R. Spectra

Though a number of dichloro-β-lactams have been prepared by us in reasonably good yield and purity, our success in the cyclisation of the eight trihaloamides were not as remarkable. A number of reactions were carried out at room temperature and at reflux temperature of benzene with the amides (III; 5, 6, 7, 8) and triethyl amine for 120 hr and above, but the product was always a mixture of amide and lactam. Reaction with alcoholic potassium hydroxide led to hydrolysis of the ester.

Recently dimsyl anion has been used for similar intramolecular alkylations. This dimsyl anion, though a strong base, is weak nucleophile.

A solution of III-7 in dimethyl sulfoxide when allowed to stand with a solution of potassium tertiary butoxide in the same reagent for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hr, gave a clear reddish brown liquid in 65-70% yield. This was characterised to be the lactam by I.R. and n.m.r. spectra.

Of the trihaloamides (III-13, 14, 15, 16) only III-14, when warmed slightly with alcoholic potassium hydroxide and allowed to stand for 30 min at room temperature, afforded 50% elimination of KCl. A solid melting at $65^{\circ}-68^{\circ}$ was isolated in 47% yield on recrystallisation. This was characterised to be the lactam by I.R. Spectra. The compound though found mildly active in vitro against a virulent strain of Entamoeba histolytica (strain STA) at 1 : 1000 dilution, could not be substantially purified to the analytical standards. The rest of the amides of this series showed hydrolysis with excess alcoholic potassium hydroxide. The I.R. Spectra showed -NH- peaks distinctly. No further attempt was made to isolate the lactams. The dimsyl anion was not as successful in the intramolecular alkylation of the haloamides of phenyl acetate series as in case of those of the malonate series.

It may be mentioned here that we tried to synthesise the following compound VII which resembles Mantamide (I) more closely than any of the β-lactams synthesised above.

The condensation of amino malonic ester (prepared by the method of V. Cerchez)¹² with benzyl chloride, gave 62% yield of Benzylamino malonate. The golden yellow liquid showed peaks at 3μ and 5.75μ in the I.R. spectrum. On chloroacylation a viscous liquid was obtained which showed a peak at 3μ

and 5.9μ respectively but eliminated a negligible amount of halogen acid on treatment with triethylamine. This is due to enhanced deactivation of the methine hydrogen by the aliphatic amido nitrogen.

Subsequent reactions with alcoholic potassium hydroxide for different lengths of time under varying temperature conditions yielded lactam as well as amide as shown by the I.R. Spectra.

Experimental

Diethyl N-(p-chlorophenyl) dichloroacetamide malonate (III-3) :

To 5.71 g diethyl p-chloroamino malonate was added 4 ml dichloroacetyl chloride and the resulting mixture heated at 110° - 12° on an oil bath for 4 hr. This was poured into ice water, extracted with benzene, washed with water till washings were neutral and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of the solvent a deep reddish brown transparent liquid was obtained. Yield 7 g (87%). The ester carbonyl and amide carbonyl peaks were shown in the I.R. Spectrum at 5.75μ and 5.9μ respectively.

1-p-Chlorophenyl-3-chloro-4-4'-dicarbethoxy-azetid-2-one (IV-3) :

6.3 g (III-3) was taken in 15 ml benzene and allowed to react with 5 ml triethylamine for 30 days at room temperature. The triethylamine hydrochloride weighed 1.98 g (90%). This precipitate was washed with benzene and the benzene extract washed free of excess triethylamine with 2 N-hydrochloric acid. It was then washed with water, dried and stripped, off the solvent. A deep reddish transparent liquid was obtained 5.0 g (80%). The I.R. Spectrum showed distinct shift of amide carbonyl absorption to lactam carbonyl at 5.65μ .

Ethyl N-(p-tolyl) α -dichloroacetamido phenyl acetate (III-10) :

A mixture of 5.4 g. ethyl α -p-toluidino phenyl acetate and 4 ml dichloroacetyl chloride was heated

on an oil bath at 125° - 130° for a period of 4 hr. On working up as III-3 white shining crystals were obtained. A number of compounds were prepared by the same procedure. Mentioned serially are the compd. numbers, solvent from which recrystallised, melting points (uncorrected) percentage yields and analytical data.

III-10, pet. ether (60° - 80°), 103° , 92%. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{19}O_3NCl_2$ C = 60.00; H = 5.00; Cl = 18.69; Found C = 59.87; H = 5.08; Cl = 18.81%. III-11, Benzene-pet. ether (40° - 60°), 109° - 110° , 90%. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{16}O_3NCl_3$ C = 53.93; H = 3.99; Cl = 26.59. Found C = 54.00; H = 4.00; Cl = 26.32%. III-12 ether-pet. ether, 112° , 93%. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{16}O_3NCl_2Br$, C = 48.54; H = 3.59; Cl = 16.00; Br = 17.99; Found C = 48.74; H = 3.83; Cl = 16.03; Br = 18.03%. Compd. III-9 was prepared similarly and the cyclisation established by I.R. Spectra.

1-p-Chlorophenyl-3,3'-dichloro-4-4'-dicarbethoxy-azetid-2-one (IV-7) :

7.7 g. of III-7 (prepared by action of trichloroacetyl chloride on diethyl p-chloroanilinomalonate) was dissolved in 20 ml DMSO. A solution of 2.2 g potassium tertiary butoxide in 55 ml DMSO was prepared and the former solution added to it slowly with shaking. On allowing the mixture to stand at room temperature for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hr removing the solvent and adding benzene to the residue, potassium chloride obtained was negligible. On washing the extract with water and adding silvernitrate to the washings 68% silver chloride was obtained. The benzene extract on usual working up provided 4.7 g (66%) reddish transparent liquid. The structure of this lactam was definitely established by I.R. and n.m.r. spectra respectively. I.R. showed peaks at 5.6 and 5.75μ . n.m.r. showed a triplet at 8.75 T for the methyl protons of the ester groups (6 protons) and a quartet at 5.75 T for the 4-methylene protons of the ester groups in addition to the 4 aromatic protons at 2.75 T

Ethyl α -trichloroacetamido phenyl acetate III-13 :

To 5.10 g. ethyl α -anilino phenyl acetate was added 2.5 ml trichloroacetyl chloride and 15 ml dry benzene and the mixture warmed for 30-45 min on a hot water bath. This was refluxed for another hour. The nonaqueous layer was then washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and stripped of the solvent. Given serially are the compound numbers, solvent from which recrystallised, melting points, percentage yields and analytical data of compounds prepared in a similar manner. III-13, benzene-pet-ether, 69° - 71° , 75%. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{16}O_3NCl_3$ C = 53.93; H = 3.99; Cl = 26.59. Found C = 54.00; H = 4.51; III-14, benzene-pet-ether (40° - 60°), 108° - 109° , 96%. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{18}NO_3Cl_3$ C = 55.00, H = 4.34, Cl = 25.52. Found C = 55.24; H = 3.83; Cl = 25.52%. III-15, 40-60 pet-ether, 120° , 84%. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{15}O_3NCl_4$ C = 49.65; H = 3.44; Cl = 32.64; Found C = 49.96, H = 3.68; Cl = 32.02%. III-16, benzene-pet-ether (40 - 60), 118° - 119° , 93%. Calcd. for $C_{18}H_{15}O_3NBrCl_3$,

C = 45.04; H = 3.12; Cl = 22.21; Br = 16.66.
 Found C = 45.39; H = 3.31; Cl = 22.00; Br =
 16.54%.

1-*p*-Tolyl-3,3'-dichloro-4-phenyl-4'-carbethoxy azetidin-
 2-one IV-14 :

2.4g. Ethyl N-(*p*-tolyl) α -trichloroacetamido phenyl
 acetate (III-14) was dissolved in dry benzene and
 3.4 ml (10%) alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution
 added to it. On slight warming a thick precipitate
 was obtained, allowing to stand at room temperature
 for 30 min yield of potassium chloride was 0.20 g
 (49%). The filtrate on working up and chilling
 overnight yielded a solid which on recrystallisation
 from ether-pet-ether showed a m.p. of 65°-68°. The
 I.R. Spectrum on purification of the compd. on
 silica gel column showed peaks at 5.6 μ and 5.75 μ
 only. The mixture melting point of the lactam
 with uncyclised amide showed distinct depression.
 Yield 1.05 g (47%).

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